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**FUNDAMENTAL AND
APPLIED RESEARCH IN
THE MODERN WORLD**

**ABSTRACTS OF VI INTERNATIONAL
SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE
JANUARY 20-22, 2021**

**BOSTON
2021**

FUNDAMENTAL AND APPLIED RESEARCH IN THE MODERN WORLD

Abstracts of VI International Scientific and Practical Conference

Boston, USA

20-22 January 2021

Boston, USA

2021

UDC 001.1

The 6th International scientific and practical conference “Fundamental and applied research in the modern world” (January 20-22, 2021) BoScience Publisher, Boston, USA. 2021. 992 p.

ISBN 978-1-73981-124-2

The recommended citation for this publication is:

Ivanov I. Analysis of the phaunistic composition of Ukraine // Fundamental and applied research in the modern world. Abstracts of the 6th International scientific and practical conference. BoScience Publisher. Boston, USA. 2021. Pp. 21-27. URL: <https://sci-conf.com.ua/vi-mezhdunarodnaya-nauchno-prakticheskaya-konferentsiya-fundamental-and-applied-research-in-the-modern-world-20-22-yanvaryaya-2021-goda-boston-ssha-arhiv/>.

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UDC 65.012

**USING A COMPUTERIZED SYSTEM TO DETERMINE THE
MOST SUITABLE JOB SKILLS FOR AEROSPACE INDUSTRY**

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Abstract: This paper proposes an idea for a new method which would help determine the most suitable skills needed for a job or a group of jobs in aerospace. The method would mostly focus on the jobs in the information technology and cybersecurity departments.

Keywords: aerospace, project team, skills, cybersecurity, hiring process

Introductions. The very first step in determining the job description for any aerospace job is to identify the skills needed for such a job. Because the jobs in the computer science department usually require a lot of not only basic, but also specific skills, it can be a challenge to narrow down the skills needed. Setting up a computerized method to determine the most needed skills for any aerospace job as well as for a specific aerospace job can greatly ease the burden on the recruitment department as well as save time and resources of the organization.

Aim. This paper aims to offer an idea for a novel method of determining the most suitable and the most needed skills to succeed in any particular aerospace job. The method will include customized recommendations and it can be utilized by any aerospace company which wishes to find a new hire.

Materials and methods. This paper requires a theoretical approach aimed at developing models, theories, and hypotheses relevant to the space industry-specific hiring methods. The research investigated in this paper is driven by numerous theories, one of which is that it is possible to significantly enhance the existing system of determining the correct job duties, responsibilities, and skills, whilst recruiting employees for the aerospace industry [1, p. 1].

Results and discussion.

The method suggested in this paper determines the most suitable skills for a particular aerospace hiring position. The first step in setting up such a system would be to write out all available and all directly and indirectly related skills which could potentially be needed to succeed in a job in the aerospace industry [2, p. 164]. Some of such skills are but not limited to: a Bachelor's or a Master's degree, a certain type of certification, a number of years of experience in the field, time spent working on a project utilizing a particular set of expertise, and many others. Generally, jobs in the information technology and cybersecurity fields require very specific skills that might not be found in candidates who used to work in other industries. For instance, an individual who had worked in the catering business may not possess the skills needed to succeed in aerospace industry. That in no way says anything about the individual's ability to learn new skills relevant to cybersecurity and such, but most of the jobs in computer science require at least some type of a background knowledge.

The next step in figuring out the most suitable skills for a particular job would be to evaluate the professionals currently working in that respective department. Then, it can be useful to find out how the skills possessed by current employees compare to the skills of a potential new hire [3, p.1]. Another question to ask is whether or not the department wants more people who have the same or similar skillset or if the department is looking for a professional with newer and different skills. Also, this method of determining the best skillset can add some general skills and basic requirements of what is required of a potential employee. For instance, some of the basic skills might be but are not limited to: a background in mathematics, knowledge of statistics, analytical thinking skills, excellent verbal and written

communication skills, the ability to pay close attention to detail, the knowledge of multiple languages, and others. The skills mentioned above are considered to be general skills, but they all still apply to the aerospace industry and can be found useful when looking at candidates' applications.

One of the most difficult parts of developing a method which establishes the job duties is that once the system calculates the skills needed and proposes them to the hiring department, the department still needs to look over the skills to make sure that nothing has been missed. Because of that, the role of the recruiting department is still crucial to the success of finding the right employee for the company. However, the computerized system which implements this novel method greatly saves the time and resources of the aerospace organization which utilizes the system. Using Big Data and Internet of Things (IoT) when handling each step of the computerized system can help greatly with the burden of categorizing and characterizing the job duties [4, p. 270].

Conclusions. The method proposed in this paper can help the hiring department in determining the most suitable and relevant skills, job duties, and responsibilities, needed for any job or a particular job in the aerospace industry. As a rule, finding a new hire in the information technology, cybersecurity, or the computer science department, requires a lot of time-consuming research about the candidates [5, p. 70]. The new computerized system can ease the burden on the recruitment department and maximize the time limits given by the company's respective departments. First of all, the system can find all available and possible skills needed for a specific job. Second of all, it can compare the skills of current employee or employees to the potential skills needed in the new employee. Also, the system can propose multiple basic skills which would be offered for review to the hiring department. Overall, with the novel method discussed in this paper there will need to be scientific experiments conducted in order to show as evidence that the method of determining the skills needed for a particular job using a computerized system is indeed efficient and would be beneficial to any aerospace organization.

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